

Open Journal System as critical knowledge infrastructure: Supporting "Open Access" from a Latin American standpoint

Abstract:

This paper examines the sociotechnical dynamics of a key technical infrastructure supporting Latin America's Open Access movement, the Open Journal System (OJS). Contrasting with the increasing adoption of Article Processing Charges (APCs) in the Anglo-European publishing space, the text highlights Latin America as a region committed to Diamond Open Access, where vibrant publishing communities support and approach, where neither authors nor readers pay nor to read or publish. This paper assesses the landscape of existing journals running OJS by repurposing installation data and parsing it with metadata from the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). Using a mixed methods approach, it leans on ethnographic research and repository analysis to present a description of key sociotechnical dynamics that support development and adoption in the region. Results discuss the key role of higher education institutions in supporting OA infrastructures, but show the limitations for keeping installations active in the region. The piece illustrates the value that intermediate layers have in supporting the translation of Open Access to local publishing cultures and, vice versa, translating local requirements to orient the development processes. These results have implications for the understanding of the sustainability of digital publishing and scientific infrastructure in the region, while stressing the key role of OJS in specific research domains.

Authors:

Matías Milia; mmilia@nd.edu (ORCID [0000-0001-8474-5373](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8474-5373))

Luis Felipe R. Murillo; lrosadom@nd.edu (ORCID [0000-0003-0563-7783](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0563-7783))

Since its conception, granting unrestricted access to scientific publications has been at the center of the Open Access (OA) movement. The assembled nature of this movement tributes to different lineages, from institutional repositories and preprint cultures, to the free culture and open-source software movements (Moore, 2017). But approaches to OA also have place-based traditions of cooperation, dissent, and collective experimentation. Latin America stands out for its regional collective push for Open Access through vigorous publishing communities and infrastructures. The community-owned nature of these contrasts with the ongoing capture of Open Access by commercial logics in the so-called developed world. Nevertheless, the long-standing region's resource constraints and the increasingly technical nature of the publishing work bring forward the question about the type of technical and institutional entities that hold this publication landscape together. This paper focuses on the region's adoption and

support of a central technical piece of infrastructure: the Open Journal System, a free and open-source software that supports the whole publication cycle of peer-reviewed academic journals.

Historically, Latin America stands out as the spearhead in developing and deploying technical infrastructure and institutional initiatives to support open access. The digital library and electronic publisher SciELO started as a pilot project in 1997 and went live in 1998 (Packer, A. L. et al., 2014), while the digital library of Open Access journals Redalyc (Becerril-García & Aguado-López, 2019) began in 2003. Formulations of Open Access as a movement happened somewhat later or simultaneously to these Latin American experiences with the Budapest (2002), Berlin (2003), and Bethesda (2003) declarations on Open Access. The early nature of the region's approach to OA somehow presents a marked contrast with the constraints of the peripheral and non-hegemonic nature of their scientific efforts (Kreimer, 2000, 2019).

In the region, the ecosystem for scientific publications rarely outsources the editorial process, and journals tend to be owned and financed by academic and scientific institutions. Publishing has traditionally been conceived as an act of making public and sharing rather than a profit-driven activity (Becerril-García & Aguado-López, 2019). This model, where neither authors nor readers get to pay to publish or access research results, is known as the Diamond Model. A quarter of journals published under this model are located in Latin America (Bosman et al., 2021).

Given the perceived status of English as the lingua franca of science (Gordin, 2015), in contexts where language publications have become a vehicle for international recognition (Meneghini & Packer, 2007) and a central component of international competition (Vessuri et al., 2014), linguistic diversity also supports other types of knowledge. Open-access journals have a specific niche in Latin American publishing (Salatino, 2017), enhancing regional circulation supported by their digitality and a common language. Outside of the mainstream circuits, they also serve specific functions critical for scientific communities, filling gaps of knowledge and serving as bridges for specific groups of readership (Chavarro et al., 2017). Language, as has been shown in other non-hegemonic contexts (Hanafi & Arvanitis, 2014), can serve as critical support for segmented circuits for knowledge circulation. Recognizing the multilingual nature of contemporary academia is crucial to decenter the dominance of English as the language of science and sustain epistemic diversity (Curry & Lillis, 2022).

The diamond publishing model poses a contrast to the increasing adoption in the United States, Europe, and Asia of author-paid Article Processing Charges (APCs) as a business model for traditional journals and for recently surged large-scale digital-native journals emulating the PLOS ONE breakthrough. The broad adoption of author-paid Article Processing Charges (APCs) shines as an instance of the transformation of OA publishing into a neoliberal market-like organization (Mirowski, 2018). This has clear ramifications for non-hegemonic countries as these charges are highly stratified (Klebel & Ross-Hellauer, 2023), which adds on top of long-standing global asymmetries in the publishing landscape. New business models have emerged in the publishing industry tied to APCs. For once, big publishers developed the so-called “transformative agreements” (Borrego et al., 2021; Pooley, 2020), refurbishing the old

idea of subscription contracts between publishers and universities, libraries, and scientific organizations. Spinning off from these changes, a new set of questionable practices seems to have emerged tied to how APCs and OA are incorporated into the business models of new and emerging publishers (Boukacem-Zeghmouri et al., 2023).

In the context of the increasing push for OA, a comparison of the evolution of publication rates in Diamond Model vs. APC-based journals has shown that author-paid papers have taken the lead in growth over the scholarly-led diamond alternatives (Bosman et al., 2021, p. 31). Although the number of articles in pay-per-publish journals is growing, the stream of documents published by diamond journals has stabilized and remained steady since 2018. These numbers point towards the robustness of a system that depends mainly on communities of volunteers or the support of scientific institutions, government agencies, learned societies, or not-for-profit publishers.

For the Latin American case, where a noncommercial structure for publishing is the norm for locally-run scientific publishing, the support of the promise of open access beyond mere accessibility has become entangled with a critical piece of infrastructure: the Open Journal System - OJS. Becerril-García and Aguado-López (2019) have stressed OJS as key in the birth of the Latin American electronic journal, providing a solution for visibility, interoperability, and presence on the web. All these features are critical components for the emergence of regional OA initiatives like SciELO, Redalyc, or Latindex.

The development of OJS has been supported by the from the early 2000s to the present, the Public Knowledge Project (PKP). The design and implementation of a major piece of infrastructure, the Open Journal System (OJS), has been a key contributor to the OA movement. The available data regarding OA presents compelling insights. Out of the approximately 5.8 million published items facilitated by OJS, 79.9% originated from the Global South, and 84.2% aligned with the OA "diamond model" (Khanna et al. 2022). What is particularly important to note is that scientific research infrastructures, such as OJS, involve substantial social and technical work that is often made invisible. This work happens, at least, in two spaces: in the development of new features and fixes for the software, and in the installation and maintenance of the platform at the journal or repository level. In the larger landscape of Open Science, OJS stands out as a piece of digital infrastructure crucial for fostering a movement for open production and circulation.

As much of the robustness of the Latin American Open Access landscape rests on the Open Journal System, the role of Latin-American contributors to the development of the software and local dynamics for the sustainability of OJS installations remains crucial. Software development, somehow placeless and placed at the same time, leans on global communities under concrete local contexts. The region has historically had a relatively low participation of developers when compared to countries like the United States, Western Europe, China, and India (Gonzalez-Barahona, 2008). Nevertheless, Latin American participation has been growing, along with developers from Asian and Eastern European Countries (Wachs et al., 2022). A connection between technology, technological development, and the exercise of power is deeply entrenched in the Latin American Free and Open Source Software landscape (Chan, 2004,

2007). Developers grounded in the region are branded by their situation as peripheral practitioners, who engage simultaneously with and try to synchronize their practices in local and global dimensions (Takhteyev, 2012). Empirical research that explores the nature of the technical and institutional entities that are backing OJS's development, design, and implementation is lacking. This paper will focus on this, expanding the limited understanding of how critical infrastructural pieces for Open Science and Open Access are developed, installed, and maintained in non-hegemonic contexts.

Methods and materials

This piece presents results that focus on the sociotechnical dynamics of OJS in the Latin American context. We build from ethnographic material resulting from interviews with developers of the system and a repository analysis. Repositories are a type of storage that centralizes a project's files and resources. They provide a trace of the units of code submitted in a project timeline and reflect the changes in the project throughout time. In Free and Open Source Software, repositories are a critical space where developers in different places share their code, resolve issues, and make collaboration happen. We draw primarily from the methodological orientation of ethnographic studies of digital infrastructures (Star 1999; Star and Ruhleder 1996; Bowker et al. 2010), triangulating qualitative and quantitative data on OJS installations and its development community.

To understand the reach of the software installations, we used different sources of information that we cleansed, merged, and parsed. We started with a list of detected OJS installations (Khanna et al., 2024) that builds on repurposed information of BEACON data (Raoni, 2024). A BEACON is a lightweight code snippet that works in the background of OJS installations and collects basic details about the installation and its content. This information, necessary for functional aspects of the platform, is collected and repurposed for research interests. Nevertheless, it still bears some limitations resulting from its original nature that can be traced to its incompleteness and limited accuracy.

In our quest to establish a more comprehensive data source for OJS installations, we turned to the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). DOAJ is a trusted, community-curated service that indexes open-access journals, ensuring they meet specific quality criteria. It indexes Open Access following the principles of the Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI, 2002). These criteria include providing information about the editorial board, sharing details about the review process, and adhering to best practices in transparency for editorial policies, author fees, or copyright information. The platform provides open access to metadata describing the journals they index (DOAJ, 2024). This long-standing, community-curated information is a valuable resource for describing well-established publishing initiatives.

DOAJ indexes journals of different types, expanding beyond those in the diamond space. Based on different identifiers, merging both databases can result in information about the OJS users being indexed in DOAJ. DOAJ indexation is then a good marker for the standardization of the editorial process, as management and technical capabilities should be in place to go through the indexation process. This source provides plenty of details about the institutional context of the publisher and the implementation of technical standards in licensing, preservation, and

machine-readability. Choosing DOAJ over regional indexes as a source of information also allows, to focus on a specific set of journals and to tap their publications into existing knowledge infrastructures for the international spread of ideas. This, when considered through the lenses of multi-linguism, provides empirical material to understand the role of language in internationalization processes.

Resorting to the CorText platform (Breucker et al., 2016), an open-science tool for STS and digital humanities research, we performed Natural Language Processing (NLP) to detect relevant terms that describe the content of the journals. First, NLP processing was conducted on keywords and subjects provided for each journal by the DOAJ index. Following this, a co-occurrence analysis was carried out to extract the underlying semantic relationships between the journals. Clusters were computed using the Louvain Algorithm (Blondel et al., 2008) in a fine-grained resolution (Aynaud, 2020) to access a more detailed description of the OSJ-DOAJ journal landscape. This analysis allowed for the emergence of a new type of categorization based on the descriptors provided for each journal by indexers.

Results

From a total of 10.491 installations reported to be using OJS in Latin America (Khanna et al., 2024), only 3.106 (29.6%) are active installations. Active installations are computed as those journals that have a steady record of at least a record of five published documents a year¹. The rate of active OJS installations is lower than in the rest of the world (35.3% of 63.875 global installations), which brings forward the limitations for electronic journal adoption of OJS in Latin America. Even in a context of wide adoption and local commitment to Diamond Access, keeping journals running appears to be challenging. Although non-technical aspects such as readership, a steady flow of submissions, funding, and institutional support can be critical for a journal's survival, professionalization and an overall technical understanding of the components of a successful journal are critical.

The development of editorial skills, pushing both technical and managerial expertise forward, is connected to the standardization of journal management and article processing, as this is something demanded by many indexing processes. It is no surprise then, that when looking at the number of OJS installations indexed by DOAJ² we find an even smaller number (966, 31,1% of the active OJS installations). This paper leans on this feature as a critical approach to understanding the use of OJS in Latin America. An analysis of this population of highly professionalized indexed journals shines as a way to understand the subset of OJS installations that have developed a sustained and well-structured management.

¹ Data goes back as much as records from 2010 and includes journals that started publishing throughout the period.

² A look to Latin American Open Access Journals indexed in DOAJ (3382 journals) where we could detect and effective install of OJS, has a ratio of adoption of 28,6% among the indexed journals.

Installations: Versions

As in other pieces of software, new versions are an opportunity for improvements, bug fixes, and changes in functionality. In the case of FOSS, the nature of these processes involves discussions between the user and developers on the best way to move forward and the prioritization of functionalities and requirements. Since 2017, OJS has released a new version of its suite, version 3. For OJS, version 3 meant a major leap in its functionalities, enhancing user experience, plug-in support, search functionalities, and better support for OA. The previous distribution, version 2, reached the end of life³ in 2021 with no more support being provided. The distribution of running journals among installed versions in Latin America and its comparison to the world total provides –see [appendix](#) for details– insight into the overall situation of OJS adoption in the region. A first salient feature is that DOAJ-indexed journals are leaning more toward v3 distribution than the other active installs in the region. Roughly 89% of these journals run on version 3, while only 84% in other electronic journals.

In Latin America, a substantial portion of the activity is supported by an older version of the software (16%), despite it having reached its end of life. These contrasts also occur when compared to international installations, where 12% of the v2 installs are still running. The survival of electronic journals in the region appears to depend more on tasks that are not heavily reliant on technical skills. When performing highly demanding technical tasks, such as updating software to a new version, journals seem to postpone it, despite, or perhaps not fully understanding, the implications for system reliability and security that this can have.

Installations

Higher education institutions in Latin America are primarily responsible for publishing electronic journals using the Open Journal System. HEIs are responsible for 78.2% (755) of the total installations –see full results [here](#)– followed by 7.9% (76) of journals run by research organizations such as study centers, research councils, or research institutes. Learned societies are responsible for another 7.3% (71), University-run editions (3%, 29), commercial editors⁴ (2.7%, 26), and the government (9, 0.9%).

Four countries (Brazil, 344 - 35,6%; Colombia, 207 - 21,4%; Argentina, 136 - 14%; Mexico, 71, 7,3%) hold 78,5% of the journals. If you include Perú (51 - 5,2%), Ecuador (40 - 4,1%), and Chile (39 - 4%), you reach 91,8% of OJS journals indexed in DOAJ. Seven countries—for a total, see the [appendix](#)—are responsible for keeping the vast majority of these publications active.

The historical legacy of Open Access in Latin America can be seen by taking a look at the historical profile of the open licenses in these seven countries. The historical depth of OA, when addressed through licenses, is very different from one country to the other. Newcomers, like

³ This has several key implications, including no more updates, limited support, and reliance on the broader community for continued functionality. This can mean higher security risks due to unpatched vulnerabilities, compatibility issues with newer technologies, and maintenance challenges as troubleshooting becomes more difficult without so many support resources.

⁴ Most of the commercial editors are small and local enterprises. Only one, Fondo de Cultura Economica has a regional tradition, although more connected to academic books.

Ecuador, had only one journal published before 2001 –for a complete account, see the [appendix](#). In Brazil 21,5% (74) of the today-active electronic journals using OJS had an open license before entering the 21st century; Colombia (38; 18.4%) and Mexico (23; 32,4%) also have an important set of legacy electronic journals. Brazil (168, 48.8%), Colombia (97, 46,9%), Chile (16, 41%), and Argentina (42, 31%) are the countries that have the region's highest percentage of new journals in the 2000s. In the next decade, from 2010 to 2020, the most active were Ecuador (29, 72,5%), Peru (34, 66.7%), Argentina (79, 58,1%), and Mexico (34, 47,9%). From 2021 to today, most of the electronic journals using open licenses are outside these seven countries.

Journal Content

Discussions about the nature of the content published in open-access journals remain critical, as it is a way of better understanding the type of discussions and the sort of communities these journals support. Suppose one wants to understand the nature of the OA movement in the region. In that case, a critical piece is to find empirical material to build a map of the topical interests of each journal as described by its editor. We have done just that, repurposing textual information provided by the DOAJ index. Content in the OJS installations indexed in DOAJ remains quite diverse regarding disciplines.

Connections between disciplines are relevant given the nature of the analysis and what it allows to capture from the open publishing landscape in Latin America. The resulting network—for an aggregated result, see [here](#); for a more detailed map, see [this interactive plot](#)—looks for the relations that bind different journals. It allows us to find terms shared by the scientific communities that support the published journals. This map shows much about the interdisciplinary links that the OA spaces enhance.

The most relevant topics in terms of size are Literature, Law, and Economics. **Economics** (Economics as a science & Economic theory), is strongly connected to development economics and political economy. **Law** (uniform law & comparative law), appears related to different branches of law, political science, and public policy. These are two essential clusters regarding volume and connections. **Literature** (Italian literature & Portuguese literature) shines as an interest in OA journals, but is highly disconnected from the rest of the landscape. A similar picture of what happens with visual arts (art history & visual arts), but the connections are more substantial to the urban settings (Human ecology & urban geography).

Other semi-peripheral interests or niche topics covered by OA journals in DOAJ are education (theory and practice & practice of education), and **library sciences** (library science & information resources). **History** (History America & Social History) and **Human Ecology** (Human Ecology & Urban Geography). Both have multidisciplinary solid connections, but is the case of Human Ecology the one that bridges better over different disciplines as mapped in our work.

Medical sciences (internal medicine & collective health) appear very much connected to public health and internal and tropical medicine branches. Veterinary sciences (Animal culture & veterinary medicine) are also an emerging concern in our mappings, although less connected than other groups. Nevertheless, their relations still suggest that journals publishing in veterinary

science share interests with other branches of biology, such as human ecology, or social sciences, as in education.

Repository Analysis.

The main purpose of OJS is to assist editorial teams by providing a web interface to manage the exchange between editors, authors, and reviewers. Its streamlined workflow guides journal managers and contributors from submission to publication. Potential authors can create an account, submit a draft, make revisions, and resubmit if needed before the piece is published with a flexible copyright license from the Creative Commons suite. Finally, publications are indexed, making them discoverable, leaning on standards like SHERPA-ROMEO, OAI-PMH, JATS, Dublin Core-DCMES, OpenGraph, DataCite, CrossRef, and are preserved through the LOCKSS (Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe) system. The Directory of Open Access Journals - DOAJ is one of the services that leans on this infrastructural work.

Based on the analysis of the source code repository, as of August 2023, the OJS project had 239 contributors and has been hosted on Github since 2004. However, this number does not accurately represent the current developers working on the project. Instead, it reflects the cumulative number from 2010 to 2023. By examining the top 5 developers annually –see full results [here](#)– we can see a more accurate representation. The project started with a small number of developers in the early 2000s but has expanded in recent years due to increased institutional adoption worldwide and the software's significance for the OA movement.

The concentration of the development duties has been strong over the years. A lot of the development has been carried out by a lead developer, Alec Smecher, now Development Associate Director of PKP. Also, the geographic distribution –a map of developers is available [here](#)– and institutional affiliation of OJS developers are particularly telling: most contributions are from Vancouver, Canada (UTC-7), where PKP was launched at Simon Fraser University. Over time, contributors aggregated from Edinburgh (UTC+0), Berlin (UTC+2), and Sao Paulo (UTC-3).

Based on data from the OJS plugin gallery (Smecher, 2024), we analyzed the contributions aimed at maintaining and expanding system features. We identified nine categories of plugin functionality: authentication, design, editorial process, functional, reporting, multilingual support, content presentation, security, and interoperability/indexing. The data reveals –a detailed account can be found [here](#)– the significant effort dedicated to improving interoperability and indexing in OJS through plug-in extensions.

Intermediaries

This institutional support is evident in the repository data for plugin work as SciELO established a collaboration with PKP in September 2018 to develop an open-source preprints server based on the existing Open Journal Systems (OJS) platform. Critical guidelines for this endeavor continue some of what is seen by the platform as the more salient features of OJS: its open software nature, its low maintenance cost, support for multilingualism, and its support for interoperability (SciELO, 2022). SciELO is a critical partner with shared values for OJS and PKP,

having established a long-lasting relationship. This is how a developer explains it in an interview:

“We have a major partnership with SciELO, a huge player in Latin America. They recognize that they depend on our software and work well with us. And so they've been supporting us for the last few years to make some major changes.”

[Interviewee 1]

Moreover, in the Latin American context, SciELO works as an intermediary between users and OJS. It has played a critical role in providing a strong connection to the region's publishing culture and helping translate Open Access to publishers, and vice versa. In the same interview, the developer adds:

“They [SciELO] have helped us set our roadmap and set priorities. And they also are a really good access point for us to understand the needs of all their various editors. If they come with us one at a time, they'll say, everyone needs this one thing. We release that one journal; we need the one thing.”

[Interviewee 1]

For Open-Source Software such as the Open Journal System, the relationship with its community of users is central to keeping the project alive and meaningful. In Latin America –as well as in other places of the world– publishers get a steady stream of academic publishing work done because of OJS. Still, the project is highly dependent on putting limited resources to good use to be able to keep providing a reliable solution for its user base. The challenge of building a community lies exactly in the same space that challenges the sustainability of the platform. In a tight space between the technical choices, the institutional spaces that use the platform, and the actual people who keep the journals running.

Sprints: building a community out of users

As this article shows, in the context of Latin America, the concept of Diamond Open Access (OA) is deeply intertwined with the university systems across various countries. While originating from a university in the North Atlantic region, the project's open and free nature, coupled with its two-decade-long technological legacy, greatly influences individuals interested in actively engaging with the development community. Connecting developers with users and maintainers becomes critical to understanding the technical challenges ahead. Shaping users into a cohesive community can, as a first barrier, involve addressing the asymmetries in technical knowledge.

And most of the folks who come in are kind of there with this like look of fear on their faces, because they're not tech folks, primarily. So then it's up to the dev[elopment] team and the folks from the hosting team.

[Interview 1]

The team is deeply engaged in the quest to weave together a cohesive community from diverse elements. They are interested in methods that will allow them to select features and determine how to provide them.

So that's helped me to have this kind of conversation. Because you have people who create plugins, you have just the editors who are asking for new features.

[Interview 2]

From this standpoint, then, it becomes essential to navigate and understand the existing assumptions regarding the roles and expectations of both developers and users. The mutual expectations for their relationship, and the resulting outcomes, underpin a guiding principle of equality, which constitutes the essence of the sprints and the relationships they promote. In practical terms, this serves as a foundational component of resource allocation, with a sense of horizontality underlying attempts to build trust in the community. A specific understanding of efficiency emerges here. First, to allocate the time spent with the community, and then, to administer the time to fulfill the requirements through coding.

For example, who attends these, to be a liaison between what people want and then the technology that allows them to do it. And the goal is actually not to have our developers sit there and type out code while somebody tells them how to do it. The goal is to collaboratively identify and solve problems that are tractable in that amount of time, in like two days.

[Interview 1]

Engaging in free and open software development can present challenges for developers. The lack of a personal link or attachment with the beneficiaries of their work can potentially drain their motivation. Sprints serve as opportunities to connect with a previously unknown community, thus embodying what was once only present in texts in forums and requests, which was, to some point, faceless. Conversation plays a critical role for both parties involved, as it facilitates the establishment of a shared path and cultivates a mutual sense of trust through the delegation of tasks.

If you know PKP Sprints, that's one of the best parts of the whole thing, like how we interact with the community. It's basically part of the team meeting with the community in different places in the world.

[Interview 2]

Sprints provide, then, an example of communal making. They build a grounded sense of commonality that is central to OJS development principles.

And during these sprints, people join and discuss different topics, connect, and learn from each other. So, it was also like learning some of these kinds of requirements or how the outside developers think about these things. That gave me some initial ideas, but basically, then it's really up to me to come up with a good solution for it.

[Interview 2]

Final remarks

Open Access and Open Science, more broadly, stand out as key milestones of ongoing transformations in the scientific space worldwide. Still, the increasing pressure of corporate enclosure towards community-run infrastructure and commons-based technologies serves as a background to analyze and understand the findings of this paper. The specificities of OJS in the Latin American context do provide critical observations that can be of help in assessing the impacts and imagining alternatives to the growing pressure of extractivist and rent-maximizing logics in the digital realm. In this sense, our empirical work has shown a fundamental tension between technical needs and available resources to sustain installations. From a total of 10,491 installations reported to be using OJS in Latin America, only 3,106 (29.6%) are active installations—a rate lower than the global average of 35.3%. This becomes even more concerning once we filter the results in journals meeting the international standards through the DOAJ indexation, as we find a smaller number (966, 31.1% of the active OJS installations). This paper has also shown that the prevalence of another practice in relation to the maintenance of these installations: a substantial portion (16%) of them is supported by versions that have reached the end of life. Our data suggest that technical needs and institutional support are not intrinsically coordinated; they happen at different levels and in different places. Journals postpone updates, to a point, dismissing the implications for the system reliability and security.

This paper has allowed us to make visible the role of professional editorial management in connection with indexing and standardization processes. Empirical findings substantiate the connection between indexing and editorial professionalization. Even in a context of limited updating practices, DOAJ-indexed journals present themselves as an active, well-maintained set of installations. This confirms how indexing and standardization processes are deeply entangled with the development of skills and editorial teams that are able to support learning paths and maintenance routines connected to journal editing in the region.

As for the regional specificities, our content analysis has presented how OJS is able to support interdisciplinary links that seem specific to the region and that relate to the region's problems. The topics that reach a more significant size, like literature, law, and economics, reflect regional priorities framing the agendas in connection with grounded intellectual debates and long-standing local needs. Economics appears to be closely connected to development and political economy, while law branches off into related fields such as political science and public policy. Literature, highly disconnected from the rest of the landscape, presents a case of a type of knowledge literature that might not find space in mainstream and English-based publishing circuits. Moreover, this paper shows how the multilingual nature of the journals analyzed here, when examined through the focus on regional topics, can stress the importance of OJS as an infrastructural support of scientific diversity. This empirical evidence confirms that OJS serves distinctive epistemic functions in Latin America beyond mere technical infrastructure.

Our repository analysis has been able to show the critical role that intermediaries play in synchronizing and managing the asymmetrical relationships users have with the software across the region. The contrast between the geographies of development and installation has not passed unnoticed and have become the center to active mediations and translations across different technical, institutional, and cultural backgrounds. These pieces of brokerage have been critical to enacting collaboration and have become central pieces for the success of the software. Ethnographic accounts from developers have shown the role that key institutional actors, like SciELO, can have in setting developing roadmaps and priorities. Deliberate spaces designed to enhance these collaborations, like the sprints, allow us to tackle and make these asymmetries productive and a critical piece of OJS sociotechnical assemblage. These practices demonstrate how connecting and assembling different skill sets and experiences emerge when focusing on defining and addressing technical issues, building a technical path that is both unique and common to different parties.

The empirical findings shared here become critical to advance the work of placing knowledge infrastructures, such as those devoted to scholarly publishing, in non-hegemonic contexts. This becomes critical to understanding implications and possibilities of alternative paths for producing and circulating knowledge. The correlation between DOAJ indexation and technical maintenance points to the importance of editorial professionalization and institutional capacity building that goes beyond mere technical training, while the content analysis reveals regionally specific research priorities demonstrating how alternative infrastructures enable forms of knowledge production that serve local intellectual communities while remaining connected to global networks.

The sustainability challenges that we documented here—from inactive installations to postponed version updates—reveal the complexities connected to infrastructural dependencies, exploring the ways links between these technologies, institutions, and people might not be sufficient to understand these dynamics. Moreover, a deeper attention to the actual practices of putting things in common through these infrastructures can be a productive way to stress the importance of understanding the communities of practices in connection to the participation and governance structures that go beyond institutional arrangements. The successful intervention of institutional intermediaries like SciELO suggests these relationships can be actively managed through strategic partnerships that account for and address asymmetries in technical knowledge and institutional capacity. The emphasis on collaborative practices, such as "sprints" and community-building efforts, reveals how infrastructure development can serve as a form of relationship-building that challenges conventional market-based sustainability models. This suggests that sustainable technical infrastructure requires ongoing horizontal collaboration between developers and users across geographic and cultural boundaries. This stresses the critical importance of an analytical framework to understand the conditions under which this purposeful work is being conducted.

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Annex

Installed versions of OJS

Version	LATAM DOAJ		LATAM OJS Active Inst.		All World OJS Active Inst.	
V 2.4	11.1%	89	16.1%	395	11.9%	7,451
V 3.0	2.6%	21	2.9%	72	4.5%	2,831
V 3.1	19.7%	158	23.8%	583	13.4%	8,344
V 3.2	18.4%	147	17.8%	437	18.3%	11,396
V 3.3	45.6%	365	36.9%	905	49.7%	30,990
V 3.4	2.6%	21	2.5%	61	2.2%	1,386
Total	100.0%	801	100.0%	2,453	100.0%	62,398

Source: OJS Installation Data (Khanna et al., 2022/2024) and DOAJ Metadata (DOAJ, 2024).

Note: not all the analyzed journals provide information about the running OJS version.

Type of Publishers

Source: OJS Installation Data (Khanna et al., 2022/2024) and DOAJ Metadata (DOAJ, 2024).

Installations by country

Country of publisher	Number of Journals	%
Brazil	344	35.61%
Colombia	207	21.43%
Argentina	136	14.08%
Mexico	71	7.35%
Peru	51	5.28%
Ecuador	40	4.14%
Chile	39	4.04%
Costa Rica	17	1.76%
Uruguay	17	1.76%
Cuba	9	0.93%
Venezuela, Bolivarian Republic of	9	0.93%
Paraguay	7	0.72%
Honduras	4	0.41%
Bolivia, Plurinational State of	3	0.31%
El Salvador	3	0.31%
Nicaragua	3	0.31%
Panama	3	0.31%
Dominican Republic	2	0.21%
Guatemala	1	0.10%

Source: OJS Installation Data (Khanna et al., 2022/2024) and DOAJ Metadata (DOAJ, 2024).

Installations by country and decade

Languages

Languages in which the journal accepts manuscripts

Source: OJS Installation Data (Khanna et al., 2022/2024) and DOAJ Metadata (DOAJ, 2024).

Top Five OJS Developers, per year (2004-2023)

	Authors	Commits (%)	Top-5 contributors	# of contributors
2023	Alec Smecher	139 (16.00% of 869)	Nate Wright, Jonas Raoni Soares da Silva, Weblate Admin, Touhidur Rahman, Bozana Bokan	74
2022	Alec Smecher	373 (15.85% of 2353)	Nate Wright, Kolbrun Reynisdottir, Tigran Zargaryan, Ieva Tiltina, Katie Cheng	126
2021	Alec Smecher	463 (20.49% of 2260)	Real Academia Galega, Dimitri Gogelia, Cyril Kamburov, Nate Wright, Madi	131
2020	Alec Smecher	606 (28.69% of 2112)	Nate Wright, Gabor Klinger, Niels Erik Frederiksen, Ramli Baharuddin, Jordi LC	97
2019	Alec Smecher	394 (44.67% of 882)	Nate Wright, thinkbulecount2, Lucia Steele, ajnyga, Pavel Pisklakov	41
2018	Alec Smecher	371 (34.38% of 1079)	Bozana Bokan, Nate Wright, bozana, Marco Tullney, algerds	41
2017	Alec Smecher	537 (30.67% of 1751)	Nate Wright, Marco Tullney, Bozana Bokan, bozana, Martin Persson	42
2016	Alec Smecher	559 (40.54% of 1379)	Marco Tullney, Nate Wright, Bozana Bokan, bozana, Bruno Beghelli	34
2015	Alec Smecher	371 (72.75% of 510)	Bruno Beghelli, Nate Wright, Marco Tullney, SamuelOPH, PKP	15
2014	Alec Smecher	329 (66.60% of 494)	Bruno Beghelli, Jason Nugent, mtub, Michael Thessel, jmacgreg	12
2013	Alec Smecher	548 (63.43% of 864)	Jason Nugent, Bruno Beghelli, jerico.dev, jmacgreg, bozana	16
2012	Alec Smecher	311 (43.80% of 710)	jerico.dev, mtub, Jason Nugent, jmacgreg, bozana	19
2011	Alec Smecher	116 (37.54% of 309)	jerico.dev, bozana, michael-pkp, Matthew Crider, jmacgreg	12
2010	Alec Smecher	312 (45.55% of 685)	jerico.dev, asmecher, Matthew Crider, James MacGregor, michael-pkp	16
2009	Alec Smecher	272 (46.66% of 583)	mcrider, jmacgreg, jalperin, michael, mj	10
2008	Alec Smecher	309 (67.61% of 457)	michael, mj, jalperin, mcrider, jmacgreg	6
2007	Alec Smecher	381 (77.91% of 489)	mj, michael, jalperin	4
2006	Alec Smecher	472 (80.14% of 589)	mj, michael, michael	5
2005	Alec Smecher	914 (59.97% of 1524)	kevin, jasonc, rory, michael, aaron	6
2004	kevin	209 (45.83% of 456)	jasonc, rory, vikram, clinton, aaron	6

List of plugins and maintainers, by institution and plugin.

Maintainer	Institution	Types of Plugins Number of plugins maintained in ()	# of Plugins
Alec Smecher	Public Knowledge Project	Auth (1), Design (1), Editorial Process (1), Func. (4), Interoperability (3), Multil. (2), Reporting (1)	13
Ronny Bölter	Leibniz Institute for Psychology (ZPID), Trier, Germany	Auth (1), Functional (4), Interoperability (3), Multilingual (2), Reporting (1)	11
University Library System	University of Pittsburgh	Design (1), Functional (3), Reporting (3), Security (3)	10
Public Knowledge Project Staff	Public Knowledge Project	Design (1), Functional (5), Interoperability (4)	10
Dulip Withanage	University of Heidelberg / Public Knowledge Project	Interoperability (4), Content Presentation (2)	6
Antti-Jussi Nygård	OJS-de.net / PKP (partially)	Editorial Process (1), Interoperability (3)	4

	<i>employed)</i>		
SciELO Brazil Online Submission and Preprints Unit	<i>SciELO in collaboration with Lepidus</i>	Editorial Process (2), Interoperability (1), Reporting (1)	4
Lepidus Tecnologia Team	<i>Lepidus Tecnologia</i>	Functional (3), Interoperability (1)	4
Vitaliy Bezsheiko	<i>Public Knowledge Project</i>	Design (3)	3
Yasiel Perez Vera	<i>Universidad La Salle</i>	Interoperability (3)	3
Matteo Mondini	<i>ReviewerCredits</i>	Interoperability (3)	3
Publons	<i>Publons</i>	Interoperability (3)	3
Manuel Campechano	<i>eScire</i>	Interoperability (3)	3
Nate Wright	<i>Public Knowledge Project</i>	Design (2)	2
Bozana Bokan	<i>Public Knowledge Project</i>	Interoperability (2)	2
Chris Maden	<i>University of Illinois</i>	Authentication (1)	1
Dimitris Sioulas	<i>National Documentation Center</i>	Content presentation (1)	1
Madi Nuralin	<i>International Information Technology University</i>	Design (1)	1
Sophy Ouch	<i>Public Knowledge Project</i>	Design (1)	1
Publishing Team	<i>University of Minnesota Libraries</i>	Design (1)	1
Alireza Sokhandan	<i>N/A (independent)</i>	Functional (1)	1
Erik Hanson	<i>Public Knowledge Project</i>	Functional (1)	1
Dimitris Efstathiou	<i>Public Knowledge Project</i>	Interoperability (1)	1
Oleksii Vodka	<i>National Technical University Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute</i>	Interoperability (1)	1
Clinton Graham	<i>Public Knowledge Project</i>	Interoperability (1)	1
Nils Weiher	<i>Public Knowledge Project</i>	Interoperability (1)	1
Team Open Access und wissenschaftliches Publizieren	<i>Universitätsbibliothek, Freie Universität Berlin</i>	Reporting (1)	1

List of plugin maintainers. Source: (Smecher, 2024)